

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DEVELOPING LISTENING SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Summary: *The article presents psychological and pedagogical characteristics of developing listening skills in primary school students in english lessons.*

Key words: *education, intellectual growth, psychological development, vocabulary, visual aids, motivation.*

The development of science and technology in the 21st century demands that young people be well-rounded, accomplished, and inquisitive. The tasks defined in the «Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan,» such as educating independently thinking youth with a personal perspective and loyalty to the Motherland, deepening democratic reforms, and increasing the social activity of young people in the process of developing civil society, are to be developed among schoolchildren, especially from elementary school age. This is the primary task of today. According to Al-Farabi, education is fundamentally aimed at shaping a person's habits and moral qualities [1]. Eastern thinkers also paid great attention to the issues of education and upbringing and were distinguished by their profound thoughts and works in this field. Their ideas also serve as a foundation for modern education.

Education and upbringing together contribute to the full development of a person. While education ensures the intellectual growth of the individual, upbringing is aimed at the development of character. Therefore, these two concepts are complementary processes and are considered key factors in acquiring knowledge, mastering social and educational norms, and finding one's place in society as an individual. Considering the above points, we must also consider the psychological and pedagogical aspects of developing listening comprehension skills in primary school students in English lessons.

The psychological characteristics of developing listening comprehension skills in English lessons depend on the psychological development of primary school students, the formation of new knowledge and skills, and their individual abilities. It is known that listening comprehension, which is the type and skill of speech activity, is the goal and means of education [2]. The following factors are crucial for developing listening comprehension skills during English lessons in elementary school:

Focusing: Primary school students' ability to concentrate is still developing. They may struggle to focus on a specific learning material or textbook for a long time. This creates difficulties for students in the process of listening comprehension. Therefore, listening materials in English lessons should be concise, engaging, and engaging for students.

Memorization: The ability to memorize information received through listening plays a crucial role in developing listening comprehension skills. Because children's memory skills are not fully developed, they may encounter difficulties in assimilating a large amount of information simultaneously. Therefore, teachers should provide concise and clear guidelines for listening comprehension exercises throughout the lesson.

Language Development: Students may not have fully mastered their native language in elementary school, which complicates their English acquisition process. Therefore, listening comprehension materials should be simple, clear, and appropriate for students' daily vocabulary.

Supporting: Most elementary school students are interested in learning a foreign language, but their interest can quickly disappear. The teacher should use interactive methods to maintain children's interest. For example, games, songs, or short videos.

Emotional condition: Students' emotional condition plays a significant role in developing their listening comprehension skills. If a student feels uncomfortable or is under intense stress, it can negatively impact their ability to listen and understand English language material. The teacher must strive to create a supportive environment for students throughout the lesson. Taking these factors into account, in the process of developing listening comprehension skills in English lessons in primary grades, teachers should choose methods that are appropriate for the psychological development of children. Using these points, we will determine the level of interest in English language lessons among elementary school students and need to scientifically analyze and address the existing psychological gaps. When developing students' listening skills in English, it is also advisable to think logically. Because we need to consider whether students can or cannot apply the words they hear in practice when speaking. The primary function of language learning is communication, which, along with expressing thought, is the primary form of reasoning. As is known, speaking and listening are two closely interconnected components of oral communication. Oral conversation is a form of communication through which communication occurs alongside listening comprehension. Therefore, learning listening comprehension and speaking skills in English lessons in elementary school is considered the main indicator of language acquisition.

Factors such as cognitive ability, motivation, and social interactions play a significant role in this process. Since elementary school students are in the early stages of cognitive development, they master new information well by completing clear and simple tasks. At this stage, students quickly absorb information through listening, which is crucial for imparting new knowledge through listening comprehension. Effective learning by listening to new sounds or words in English contributes to the development of English speaking skills. To support cognitive development, teachers should focus on simple, engaging listening skills, such as songs, stories, and repetition-based activities. To enhance students' understanding, it is beneficial to complete tasks combined with visual aids [3].

One of the psychological factors in learning English is motivation, which plays a key role in students' perception and understanding of information. If tasks, engaging interactions, and group work are included, students will be more engaged. If the learning process is free from supportive and psychological pressure, students can engage in conversational (speech) activities without fear of making mistakes. "Success in language learning depends on many factors, particularly motivation. Motivation is the driving force that encourages a learner to strive to achieve their goals"[4]. Therefore, motivation (rewarding) helps students overcome psychological pressure during the lesson, ensures active participation in the lesson, and makes the learning process more effective. The importance of motivation can be classified as follows.

1. To increase student interest in the lesson, develop the use of poems and stories as the main part of the lesson.
2. To foster a positive attitude towards learning a foreign language in students by completing rewarding tasks. For example, small gifts or game-based tasks stimulate children's interest in the lesson.
3. Increasing self-confidence strengthens students' confidence in their ability to perform listening comprehension exercises. Rewarding and grading students helps them continue the lesson without fear of mistakes. Taking the above into account, motivation in students can be developed as follows.

Using interesting materials, select stories and simple dialogues that are appropriate for the students' age.

Gradual transition from simple and easy-to-understand materials to complex exercises.

By evaluating the results of listening comprehension, further increase students' interest in completing the exercises.

The use of interactive methods develops students' skills in working in groups. For example, using games like «who answers quickly» or «find the answer by listening» during the lesson.

In conclusion, the role of motivation in listening comprehension exercises in English lessons is very significant. Properly formed motivation helps students develop listening comprehension skills and enjoy the language learning process. Encouraging and engaging activities increase motivation and strengthen students' self-confidence in the language learning process.

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